
Leading A School: A Challenging Task for Head Master

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ABSTRACT

In the era of rapidly changing society and its norms due to globalization. The most powerful medium to reach common people for their welfare is healthy schooling system. An ideal school is an inspiring pillar for nation to develop healthy feeling among common people of the country. Overall, headmaster is considered as a key person who can make or mar the society or entire education system especially foundation pillar of education i.e. primary education. So, he should be full of energetic ideas and sound personality along with his responsibility for effective quality management. With his special qualification and long experience, he can help all the students and staff to coordinate among themselves and make the school functioning effective. In this paper, we endeavor to highlight the qualities of headmaster to tackle the school problems effectively and boost up the healthy environment in the school.

Introduction

Education is known as the key to nation's progress. Iwantoro (2014) stated that education is an important issue for the development of the nation and country. The head master is considered as the academic leader, administrative planner and guide of the primary school and responsible for everything what takes or happens within in the school for teaching to management whether poorly or effectively. He is the person of running a primary school and manages both teaching and administration, ensuring that

education and discipline are properly and effectively maintained. He acts as a bridge between education department, students and community.

Significance/ Role of A Good Head Master in School Management

The success or failure largely depends upon the head master's leadership, vision and his dedication towards the school. He builds a bridge between teachers, parents and community along with students. He supervises the teachers and ensures effective teaching learning outcomes. school discipline and administrative works are of his prime task. Improvement in educational quality emphasizes strongly on the importance of the role of school and role of principal/headmaster in developing education and developing educational conditions.

In olden days, head master was primarily seen as a record keeper. However, with the advent of modern education, all the managers, child centered education, head master's role has expanded a lot. Now, he is considered a visionary leader and a community developer, not merely as an academic administration. Anzar and Mardhatillah (2018) stated that school learning activities are a major activity in the improvement of quality of national education Rashid and Wahap (2024) reported that the head's transformational leadership and teacher quality both have a high and significant relationship, according to the results obtained by the Pearson Correlation test ($r=0.59$, $p<0.01$). in brief, the leadership practices practiced by head teachers usually affect the quality of the school's day to day practices.

Objectives of the Study

- O1 To make clear of the concept of school management and supervision
- O2 To mention the duties and Responsibilities of head master towards the school
- O3 To highlight the rights/Powers of headmaster
- O4 To suggest the qualities required to be a good head master
- O5 To mention the programs which a leader can boost up himself

School Management and Supervision

School management refers to all the process of planning, organizing, directing and controlling the school activities effectively to achieve the educational goals ie to ensure providing the quality education to the students.

Main functions of school management are mainly four in number- planning, organizing, directing and controlling. The complete process is called school management

The Duties and Responsibilities of Head Master

The headmaster is basically a senior teacher with the great responsibility for the management of school (Sharma, Pathak and Kumar, 2021). Following are the duties and responsibilities-

(A) Academic Leadership

- To supervise the teaching staff in lesson planning and teaching methods
- To ensure the effective outcomes of the students' learning
- To organize and monitor regular assessment and progress of the students

(B) Administrative work

- To maintain the school records, attendance register and confidential order or papers and reports
- To help in implementing government and education department rules in the school education system
- To help in preparing in time table, distributing workload and managing the admissions

(C) Supervision and Discipline

- To maintain the discipline among the students and staff
- To help in ensuring healthy and friendly learning environment

(D) Community and Parents Relationship

- To communicate with parents on PTM day and school management committee
- To promote the nearby community to involve in the school activities

(E) Financial Management

- To manage and consume the funds and grants properly
- To keep the records of expenses and utilization very clear

(F) Training and Development

- To encourage the existing teachers to participate in the training and formal practices and to attend training program and work shops
- To keep the staff updated with modern teaching practices

The Rights of Headmaster

- To assign the duties to teachers and other staff members

- To grant leave to staff as per rules
- To recommend teachers and other staff for promotion
- To disciplinary action against whenever needed
- To represent the school performance before higher authorities whenever they visit the school

The Qualities Required to be a Good Head Master

- To have leadership and good decision power
- To be full of honesty and fairness
- Good communication skill and management skill to tackle the problem of school effectively
- To show love and sympathy towards students
- To have knowledge of modern educational trends
- To have ability to inspire team work and co-operation

The Programs Which a Leader Can Boost Up Himself

Educational management is a particular work. The headmaster ought to principally be an educational master and should check out crafted by all teachers as stated by Lidbe and Upadhyay (2019). He should do-

- Should have a diploma or degree as set by state government
- Should have work experience
- To have good personality traits
- Should have extensive expertise

Asmani (2014) reveals that headmaster has several tasks namely- planning, organizing, briefing, co-ordination. He should try to keep his pace with the existing practices as in India.

Conclusion

Headmaster in the school plays a vital role in shaping the nation's future. He has to play different roles like an educator, manager, administrator, supervisor, innovator and motivator etc. A good headmaster can improve the quality of education system by helping the teaching staff continuously who are less competent via communication and campaigning on quality of education with his teaching staff. With his high vision, he can meet the shortage of teachers, lack of motivation in the transfer willing teachers and near to retirement, in both cases, a good head master can meet the needs of teachers, students and parents

along with community needs successfully. Musdiani (2018) reported that the headmaster acts as a function of encouragement, influence, in an educational organization and as an examples for educators.

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